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Towards the digitalization and automation of circular and sustainable construction and demolition waste management – project RECONMATIC

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Abstract. The construction sector is responsible for a large part of CO₂ emissions, consumption of resources and generation of waste globally. Although the importance of construction and demolition waste management in a circular and sustainable way has been acknowledged on an academic and policy level, there are still steps needed to be taken both in terms of expanding the use of such principles in waste management frameworks but also in terms of increasing their efficiency through the digitalization and automation of their processes. This article provides a presentation of the RECONMATIC project, a Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action project, that aims to develop novel tools, technologies and methodologies that can contribute in such a manner in multiple construction phases and project types or material and product life cycle stages.

1. Introduction

The construction sector is a major contributor to global CO₂ emissions [1] resource consumption and waste generation [2] and its growth is closely linked to the increasing urbanization trends throughout the globe. Even in highly urbanized regions however, as is the case for Europe, it is responsible for a half of total raw material extraction and more than a third of waste production. The management of construction and demolition waste (CDW) is thus considered of critical importance in EU policies [3]. These findings are consistent with the fact that CDW is generated throughout various stages of the life cycle of construction projects (construction, refurbishment/maintenance, demolition) and highlight the need to take them all into account in waste management frameworks [4].

In order to achieve waste minimization and valorization, notions like the waste hierarchy and circularity have been introduced in such frameworks, on both an academic and policy level. Although quite similar, the former prioritizes prevention, reuse, recycling, recovery and as a last resort disposal of waste, while the latter does not allow disposal, aiming to close material loops [3]. While the structure of this hierarchy significantly enhances waste minimization efforts, it does not directly address the various treatment options in terms of resource efficiency [5]. In the EU, many countries report high CDW recovery rates, that are however mainly accomplished through backfilling, a low value recovery alternative [6]. Concepts that support the transition from waste to natural resource management [7] must be employed, in order to ensure that material value is considered, preserved and added. These should not only be applied to evaluate end-of-life alternatives, but also options for all

building life cycle stages, including design, construction and refurbishment, which hold great potential in preventing resource use and waste generation [3].

Assessing such value is nonetheless a complex issue that in many cases calls for multiple trade-offs between environmental and economic [2] or even social parameters for a complete sustainability evaluation of the waste management chain [8] and bears the potential to contradict the priorities set by the waste hierarchy [3]. In addition, since processes such as construction material selection [9] and related extraction of resources and product manufacturing [10] appear to have significant impacts in several aspects of buildings' sustainability, respective assessments should consider the whole life cycle of construction materials, products and components included in them.

Together with the theoretic framework of parameters and information to be considered for an efficient CDW management scheme, a supporting technological structure needs to be developed. The lack of an integrated information management system and of tool interoperability have been identified as major technological barriers for the adoption of circularity in the construction sector. Waste recognition, sorting and certification tools, data handling, mapping and design tools integrated or interoperable with BIM applications are some examples of required solutions to be developed [1].

Summarizing, it could be argued that an efficient CDW management framework should incorporate:

- circularity, waste hierarchy and resource efficiency principles, to ensure waste minimization and valorization,
- a sustainability (environmental, economic, social) life cycle perspective, both on a building or construction project scale, but also on an individual material, product and component level,
- efficient information management and automation of processes, using digital tools and platforms,

in order to provide effective and holistic decision-making and execution, that achieves a desired equilibrium of sustainability factors using circularity and resource efficiency methods.

The RECONMATIC project, a Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action project, aims to contribute to this direction, by providing several digitalizing and automating solutions of various CDW management aspects, while considering and enhancing their sustainability and circularity performance. Although not aspiring to complete integration, it also aims to combine various selections of these solutions in several appropriate real-life applications, with the ultimate goal of providing innovative and practical CDW management interventions, that can contribute significantly to the achievement of EU environmental goals, such as the zero CDW by 2050 target.

The following chapters of this article present the general structure of the project, its key deliverables and its demonstration cases. A more in-depth analysis is provided for the solution and case that concern fresh concrete waste management, which represents a major portion of CDW [3]. The Aristotle University of Thessaloniki is a leading partner for the development of these fresh concrete solutions.

2. General project scope and structure

In accordance with the goals set for the project, several tools, technologies and methodologies for sustainable and circular CDW management are to be developed, formulating interventions that collectively aim to cover the whole life cycle of construction projects (buildings and other civil infrastructure), waste materials (off-site treatment and secondary material production) and the need for integrated information management, sustainability and circularity assessment.

Once they are developed, their real-life application will be evaluated through six demonstration cases in five European countries. Each one of these cases will represent a different type of construction project or CDW management aspect and will utilize an appropriate selection of the tools

produced. Their outcomes in terms of sustainability and circularity will afterwards be assessed with the help of a tool also developed as part of the greater project.

In addition, dissemination efforts of the knowledge produced will be undertaken along the project's timeline, and training programs will be offered in its latter stages.

The following chapters present a brief overview of key project deliverables and the project's demonstration cases.

3. Key deliverables

The key tools, technologies and methodologies to be developed in the project are categorized below based on common CDW management aspects they aim to address.

3.1. Information management

3.1.1. Digital Information Management System (DIMS). A digital platform able to perform dataset hosting and linking to BIM models, to function as a common data environment for the various work package teams of the project but also for the various waste management stakeholders required to participate in each one of them. It is expected to enhance life cycle waste traceability, stakeholder collaboration and assist in performance tracking of the various other tools developed in the project.

3.2. Design and construction phase of buildings and infrastructure

3.2.1. Materials Data Bank (MDB). Establishment of a methodology and creation of digital platform that allows linking cloud-based datasets and BIM authoring tools (e.g. Revit) in order to streamline the material mapping process, including among others, information about material recyclability and secondary product requirements.

3.2.2. WASTEie. A new set of attributes for BIM objects that will function as a common data standard for documenting, analysing and exchanging information related to the recyclability/waste production potential of building and civil infrastructure materials, components or systems.

3.2.3. Waste predictor application. BIM-integrated software that will enable waste generation or recovery (and associated costs) predictions in the design stage of construction projects, based on the materials and construction technologies considered in design alternatives.

3.2.4. Generative design platform. A platform utilizing the above-mentioned as well as other tools, to perform generative design iterations through plug-ins in BIM authoring applications, with the goal of optimising waste generation early in the life of a construction project.

3.3. Refurbishment/repurposing, deconstruction and demolition phase of buildings and infrastructure

3.3.1. Automated creation of digital twin of end of service life (EoSL) construction/structures. Creation of the digital twin of EoSL buildings and other construction infrastructure through the combination of digitized 2D drawings, UAV images and Structures-from-Motion algorithms, 3D scanning of indoor spaces with AI-based point cloud localization and material properties allocation.

3.3.2. Extensive database of EoSL materials and products properties. A database that will be formed through the collection of information concerning among others the EoSL properties of construction materials (type, mechanical properties), requirements and outlets for potential reuse/recycling, treatment options, types of potential secondary materials and relevant market data.

3.3.3. Automated decision-making system for CDW audit and deconstruction and demolition planning. Building on the two previous tools, a digital tool automating the process of waste auditing

and demolition/deconstruction planning will be developed, with the aim of minimizing waste production and downcycling, considering a wide array of factors (material and component estimated current status, spatial and weather conditions, health and safety risks and others).

3.4. Off-site CDW management and treatment automation

3.4.1. Automated robotic line for off-site CDW sorting and pre-treatment. Based on extensive CDW sampling, tests of low-costs sensors and AI algorithms and the development of a convolutional neural network system employing additional sensors such as hyperspectral cameras, to create a deep learning system for CDW recognition, classification and localization along the treatment line. To be combined with it and apply its potential, a novel sorting robot that employs pick-and-throw instead of pick-and-place processes and its accommodating line configurations will then be developed, with the aim of increasing productivity, recover/recyclability rates but also purity of output materials from contaminants.

3.4.2. Methodology for improved CDW management. Collection of current practices and regulations regarding CDW management and provision of a modified framework for it that considers the potential changes in output purity, quality monitoring, quality of secondary products or other effects a system such as the abovementioned can bring about. Recommendations for CDW sorting, secondary material market practices, improved waste collection (logistics chain, waste container specifications), and recycling plant organization and geographic allocation will be included.

3.5. Secondary material production

3.5.1. Digitized quality control and assurance mechanism. As a first step, through the collection and evaluation of data from various teams and subprojects and extensive non-destructive material testing, a dataset and methodologies that aim to increase the valorization of waste will be developed, through determining material conditions and considering reuse/recycling requirements, market uptake, certification and traceability requirements and regulations for secondary materials and ways to overcome relevant barriers, possible future uses and other factors, in order to be integrated with other project tools. As a next step, a testing methodology will be developed to ensure quality procedures are followed and a digital tool for remotely monitoring and controlling such procedures for cases when lab testing is not possible (e.g. on-site testing of CDW mixtures).

3.6. Sustainability and circularity assessment

3.6.1. Digital tool for sustainability and circularity assessment. Criteria and methodologies for sustainability (environmental, social, economic) and circularity assessment will be collected and evaluated, along with input from multiple stakeholder categories and green building certification, life cycle assessment (LCA) and other sustainable construction guidelines and standards. These will then be utilized to develop a digital tool (and an accompanying guide) that incorporates an assessment methodology and key performance indicators (KPIs) relevant to the tools and technologies to be produced through the project. This tool will be integrated with the DIMS in order to help with their performance tracking and final evaluation.

4. Demonstration cases

4.1. BIM-based platform for waste optimization in the design and construction stage of buildings and infrastructure (UK)

Demonstration and validation of a BIM-based platform that integrates the developed Materials Data Bank and Waste Prediction tools through utilizing the WASTEie data standard and that on a more

advanced level provides data to the Generative Design tool, in order to achieve waste optimization through the consideration of numerous design solutions.

4.2. Digital management of materials and CDW in railway infrastructure (Italy)

Enrichment of 5D BIM of a railway project, using a combination of the MDB, Waste Predictor software and WASTEie data standard, material information, multiple design and construction stakeholders input, UAV surveying technologies and the DIMS to form an open data sharing platform that can function as a 7D BIM hub for facility and asset management, enhancing waste traceability, but also as a design optimization platform that enables waste minimizing throughout all the interventions required in the project's life cycle.

4.3. Digital twin of road infrastructure for CDW management automation (Czech Republic or Slovakia)

The BIM-based digital twin of an existing road structure will be created at first, using the tools developed for this purpose and will be characterized with material and waste information. From then on, a platform of similar philosophy to the one previously mentioned will be developed, employing the BIM-based waste optimization tools, digital material and component databases, multiple surveying technologies and other tools to ensure waste traceability throughout the structure's life cycle, and waste minimization in the design of rehabilitation works. For new materials required, automated lean logistics applications will also be used.

4.4. Digital twin of buildings for CDW management automation (Czech Republic)

A selection of the tools developed in the project (EoSL and treatment options databases, automatic creation of digital twin, automatic audit and deconstruction planning, BIM-based waste tools) will be employed to enhance the waste management aspect of building design, refurbishment and demolition works, with focus on specific waste streams (mainly gypsum – gypsum board partitions). Refurbishment stage: the digital twin of a to be refurbished building will be created and enriched with material and waste information, to perform deconstruction planning and execution (using segregated demolition to achieve waste minimization and purity increase). Design and construction: design and assembly solutions for the refurbishment of the building (or creation of a new one) will be developed using the BIM waste prediction/minimization tools but also the data for treatment options, to ensure waste valorisation as well.

The reuse of gypsum components in the renovated building will also be demonstrated, as well as the secondary material production through recycling.

4.5. Automated off-site CDW treatment and valorization (Spain)

Real-life application, in a CDW management facility, of the off-site CDW automated sorting robotic line and digitized quality assurance and control mechanism, in order to evaluate and demonstrate their functional and economic effectiveness. These will be assessed in terms of minimizing output flow contamination from materials such as gypsum and glass (compared to manual sorting lines), manual labor and costs decrease for the sorting process, and secondary material quality and standard compliance to ensure market uptake. Research and testing will also be conducted on the utilization of low-cost sensors and AI algorithms in order to examine the potential of upscaling the adoption of the automated line through minimizing the associated investment costs.

5. Tool and demonstration case for fresh concrete waste minimization

5.1. Smart fresh concrete logistics tool

It will be based on a digital platform that incorporates Internet of Things (IoT), GPS, AI and blockchain technologies and smart sensors to form a decentralised digital framework that enables the

employment of lean practices throughout the whole production and logistics supply chain of fresh concrete, while ensuring transparency and safety in all transactions.

More specifically, it will provide the following features:

- Electronic order placement from site engineers and contractors to the concrete plant, adjustable on the basis of changing concrete requirements or environment/weather conditions.
- Order management optimization for the plant, based on its production and delivery capacity and order quantities and distances.
- Order tracking and provision of delivery time estimation to the site engineers, to support better project management and scheduling, in order to minimize the time fresh concrete remains inside trucks.
- Concrete truck location and route tracking, monitoring of concrete and environment conditions throughout the transport's duration, to assess its properties and potentially enable the matchmaking of fresh concrete surplus to secondary uses on other sites.
- Safeguarding of the transparency and security of information relevant to the production, transport, delivery, and material properties of concrete batches through utilizing a decentralized blockchain framework.
- Collection and recording of data important for LCAs (e.g. on concrete transport fuel consumption and emissions).

5.2. Demonstration case: Reducing concrete waste in the production, construction phase and promoting its reuse/recycling (Greece)

The abovementioned smart logistics platform will be tested in various construction projects in Greece, to evaluate its performance in reducing concrete waste through lean production and delivery or potential immediate reuse of fresh concrete surplus in other sites or for other purposes.

Furthermore, measures aiming to streamline the recycling process of concrete returned to the plant will be applied such as:

- Automated water circulating system for truck washing that enables recirculating it and eventually introducing it to the concrete mixer.
- Fuel contamination and pH monitoring of the decanting pool and automation of its water circulating system.
- Water consumption monitoring in the plant.
- Testing of the use of wash water in subsequent concrete batches.
- Testing of the properties of mineral recycled aggregates produced by the crushing of solid concrete waste from the decanting pools but also of the properties of new concrete batches using them as aggregate substitutes (identifying optimal mixing proportions).
- Sustainability (environmental, economic, social) assessment of the waste value chain of concrete.

6. Conclusions

Although the importance of CDW management has been recognized both in the research community but also in terms of applied policies in the EU or throughout the world, further enhancements need to be made in terms of the circularity, sustainability and efficiency of correspondent waste management frameworks and their individual processes, in an effort to achieve set environmental goals, such as the EU target for zero CDW by 2050.

This article presented the goals, deliverables and demonstration cases included in the RECONMATIC project, that aims to provide tools, technologies and methodologies that promote the digitalization and automation of CDW management processes, while utilizing circularity and sustainability principles. They concern a wide range of construction projects and their life cycle stages,

as well various processes encompassing the life cycle of individual materials and waste streams, from production to reuse or recycling.

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